

Situationally-Induced Impairments and Child Care: The Case of Browsing an Audio Streaming Platform In Kangaroo Care

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ABSTRACT

Neonatal care poses unique challenges for parents of premature babies, particularly during kangaroo care, a practice involving prolonged skin-to-skin contact to promote infant health and bonding. While beneficial, this method restricts mobility and requires a calm, low sensory stimulation environment. Many parents turn to audio content, such as music or podcasts, for relaxation and to shield against noise. However, conventional audio streaming platform (ASP) interfaces rely heavily on visual and manual input, making them difficult to use in these conditions. Through interviews and questionnaires with parents, we identified how situationally-induced impairments (SIIs) caused by kangaroo care hinder interactions with ASPs. To address these challenges, we propose to test a design concept (originally targeted to cater to SIIs more generally) involving on-body sensors, gesture-based interaction and multimodal feedback. These solutions enable intuitive audio management with minimal visual or manual reliance, enhancing accessibility and, presumably, supporting caregiver well-being. This work highlights the importance of inclusive, multimodal designs for contexts like neonatal care and contributes to broader accessibility efforts for users experiencing SIIs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Listening to audio content, such as music, podcasts, and audiobooks, is a common way for people to relax, focus, or escape everyday stressors. However, accessing and controlling this content often relies heavily on visual and manual interaction with digital platforms like Spotify, YouTube Music, or Audible. Such *audio streaming platforms* (ASPs) provide users with access to an expansive universe of audio content, and invoke deep personalisation to curate recommendations [1, 2].

An ASP's success in delivering a value-enriched user experience also depends on its ability to facilitate dynamic exploration: empower users to navigate through recommendations and content easily, and make decisions with less effort. However, this proposition, along with the high information density involved, introduces accessibility challenges. Engagement with an ASP while simultaneously engaged

in other activities like commuting, exercising, doing domestic tasks, or taking care of children, influences their interaction styles, navigation patterns and browsing choices. In such cases, users may experience varying degrees of *situationally-induced impairments* (SIIs): impairments in perceptive or cognitive capabilities that occur when external contextually-imposed factors place temporary constraints on the user [3]. The expression of SIIs are usually dynamic in nature since the contextual situation imposing the SIIs are often dynamic themselves, placing time-variant demands on the user's abilities.

One context where challenges of SIIs and interaction become pronounced is in neonatal care, specifically during *Kangaroo Care* where parents lie with their premature babies on their chest in prolonged periods of skin-to-skin contact [4]. It is common for kangaroo care to last for extended periods, up to several weeks. While kangaroo care is beneficial for the infant's health and bonding, it can be extremely stressful to parents for a number of reasons. Many parents engage with audio content for personal relaxation, as an auditory shield against background noise, or to regulate sleep. However, the anticipated low-stimulation situation of kangaroo care and the position of the child drastically restrict their freedom of movement. Visual and manual interaction with audio players gets impractical with risk of disrupting the contact with the baby.

The first author has developed SII-accommodating concepts for ASP interfaces that utilise gesture-based controls and spreads feedback between multiple modalities such as audio and haptic cues, to replace over-reliance on interactions with visual-heavy interfaces. That work builds on principles of *Ability-Based Design* (ABD), a sister-framework for accessible computing that advocates harnessing the potential of working with user abilities and environmental affordances [5, 6]. This design conceptualisation addresses broader implications for accessible interfaces for any scenario where SIIs restrict sensory or attentional resources—including those where the user is mobile, 'on-the-go'.

In this study, we probe how SIIs imposed on a user's physical, sensory and cognitive abilities when they're in a highly demanding contextual situation like kangaroo care can affect their interactions with ASPs, and explore accessible design solutions that accommodate their abilities. The developed concept designs aim to empower users to intuitively manage audio content without compromising their ongoing activities—in this case facilitating and administering kangaroo care. By investigating how to design accessible

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experiences to accommodate these unique challenges, we contribute to inclusive design approaches that account for diverse user needs in real-world, constrained environments.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Situationally-Induced Impairments

Situationally-induced impairments occur when an individual's abilities are temporarily limited by situational factors (specific circumstances), contextual factors (goals, state, and purpose), or environmental factors (physical and social setting) [3]; see also the World Health Organization's 2020 policy on disability. With ubiquitous computing, these impairments are increasingly relevant as varying situations introduce new challenges for interaction.

Factors contributing to SIIs include behavioral (e.g., walking [7], encumbrance [8]), environmental (e.g., noise, cold, out-of-reach devices [9]), attentional (e.g., multitasking [10], cognitive overload [11]), and affective, social, and technological (e.g., stress, norms, small devices). Designing with SIIs in mind enables adaptable, inclusive solutions—for example, a smartphone operable with one hand benefits both someone holding a baby and a person with one arm [3]. Despite progress, many devices lack situational awareness, necessitating further development in context-aware technology.

2.2 Frameworks in Accessible Computing

Accessible computing has evolved through various frameworks: Early frameworks, like Assistive Technology, provided tools for users with disabilities but risked stigmatization through add-on solutions [12]. Universal Design, influenced by the limitations of Assistive Technology, emphasized “one-size-fits-all” inclusivity but proved too rigid for personalized digital interactions [5]. Design for All aimed to extend accessibility into the digital realm but primarily addressed general rather than individual needs [13]. Similarly, Inclusive Design sought to minimize exclusion by considering diverse user abilities but struggled to scale due to designers' unconscious biases and limited capacity to account for all needs [14].

Building on these approaches, the Ability-Based Design (ABD) framework prioritizes user strengths and shifts the burden of adaptation from the user to the system [6]. The seven ABD principles¹ advocate for flexible, scalable, and dignity-preserving technologies that work with what users can do, asking, “*What can you do?*” rather than “*What can everyone do?*” [5]. This study employs the ABD framework to contextualize its findings in accessible computing.

2.3 Hands-Free Interaction

Voice- and gesture-based interaction enables users to control devices in an intuitive, mostly hands-free experience, which is useful when visual attention or touch input is limited [15]. Several commercial solutions exist for hands-free interaction; this is especially true for voice commands which are

¹ Ability, Accountability, Adaptation, Transparency, Performance, Context, Simplicity

widely accepted [16]. Dedicated gesture-based interaction has been popularized in console game architectures like Nintendo Wii and Kinect [17], and more recently virtual reality headsets, but still without reaching the same level of acceptance as voice input, or even succeeding in establishing standards for gesture input [18]. In the following we discuss some of the strategies in gesture-based input relevant to SIIs interaction with a handheld device.

One typical characteristic of many SII situations is an incapacity to use both hands normally, for instance when commuting. With this limitation, a device may be operated in different ways: *Same-side interaction* involves using the body part carrying the device to operate it, such as controlling a smartphone with the same hand that holds it. Examples include tilt-navigation [19] and wrist-as-joystick systems [20]. Although convenient, this method has mobility and visibility limitations [21]. *Opposite-side interaction* employs other body parts for control, such as the free hand manipulating a smartwatch, supporting more flexible, precise interactions, as seen in extended touchscreens [22] or multimodal touch-input methods [23].

Studies have proposed guidelines for designing gesture-based systems tailored to different contexts. Examples include mid-air gestures for blind users interacting with TVs [24], touchscreen adaptations [14], and motion gestures for hands-free TV control [25]. However, there is limited research on designing gesture protocols for users with situational impairments in high-information, mobile contexts like adaptive digital platforms.

There are several participatory approaches to gesture interaction design. Context-focused ideation aligns gestures with natural body movements [26], and device-focused elicitation invites users to propose gestures that are easy to learn and recall. Mixed approaches, combining user proposals and curated options, enhance accessibility [24].

2.4 Neonatal Care Units and Kangaroo Care

Premature infants, born before 37 weeks of gestation, often face significant health challenges. Neonatal care focuses on supporting these infants' survival and development, often requiring specialized interventions provided in Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs): equipped medical environments offering life-sustaining treatments. While these units are vital for stabilizing premature infants, they can also be stressful for parents due to the medicalized setting [27]. When intensive care is not required, infants and their parents are moved to regular neonatal care units, often called family rooms.

Kangaroo care is a neonatal care method where an infant is placed skin-to-skin on a caregiver's chest [4]. Originating in the late 1970s as an alternative to incubators in resource-limited settings, the method is now globally recognized for its numerous benefits, including promoting thermal regulation, improving oxygenation, fostering breastfeeding, and strengthening parent-infant bonding.

Premature infants are typically connected to various medical devices, which makes the practice of kangaroo care challenging. Providing this type of care requires the parent to remain stationary for periods of up to several hours, or to

carefully reposition and lift the infant when movement, such as getting up for nursing, is necessary. During the parent's waking hours, they are expected to maintain silence.

3. METHOD

The study's method includes 1) a discovery phase interview process, 2) an ideation workshop, followed by a conceptualisation including a video prototype, and finally, 3) interviews with parents with lived experiences of neonatal care to probe an extreme case of SIIs. Participants were recruited through convenience sampling, with separate, non-overlapping groups for each of the three stages.

3.1 Discovery Research: Semi-Structured Interviews

Before the discovery research interview, participants documented their habits around audio content consumption. The interviews lasted 25–30 minutes and focused on when and how participants engaged with ASPs and audio content while being simultaneously engaged in another activity, how their environment and devices influenced their experience, and how they adapted to challenges. We avoided using terms like 'SIIs' to prevent bias, adhering to ABD principles. The interviews were recorded and transcribed, with a thematic analysis conducted to form insights.

3.2 Generative Ideation: Participatory Workshop

The goal of the workshop was to explore how users envision engaging in a listening session and interacting with their ASPs without relying on touching screen-based or reading visual-heavy interfaces. The participants were divided into two groups based on their audio engagement habits. The workshop had three phases, lasting 180 minutes:

Phase 1—Divergent Ideation: All participants were introduced to 'STUIQUIBOU', a hypothetical screenless and omnipresent ASP, conceptualised to encourage creativity by eliminating current technological limitations. They were instructed to brainstorm and sketch ideas for interacting with this omnipresent ASP using body gestures and sounds.

Phase 2—Prioritisation: The two groups were assigned a contextual situation each (chosen based on their audio engagement habits) to consider how they would interact with 'STUIQUIBOU' using their body gestures in such situations. They identified and prioritised body parts and gestures for interaction based on the context and the abilities they could exercise.

Phase 3—Concept Development: Each group was instructed to design a gesture-based interaction protocol, the supporting on-body artefact, and map out interaction flows and expected feedback from their on-body artefact. Participants considered social factors and ease of use while conceptualising, and communicated their concepts by role-play and demonstration.

The workshop was documented using audio recordings, photos, and written notes. Afterward, the recordings and sketches were transcribed, reviewed, and analysed using an inductive approach to identify key insights.

3.3 Conceptualisation and Realisation

We synthesized findings from the research and prior studies on gesture-based interaction to develop a proposed concept. This concept was sketched, role-played, and tested in two scenarios to assess gesture affordances and sensor data. Low-fidelity prototypes were created and refined into higher-fidelity versions using Figma. A video prototype was developed to demonstrate the concept.

3.4 Contextualising for Kangaroo Care

Finally, we recruited parents from a specialized social media group who had premature infants and had completed a neonatal unit stay of at least two weeks. For this study, the participants were not informed about the design concepts, SIIs, or problems of interacting with ASPs. We conducted both structured interviews and questionnaires which used a 5-step Likert scale response method. The interviews explored topics such as sleep deprivation and the impact of light and sound design in neonatal units, while the questionnaires focused on issues related to alarms, disturbances, kangaroo care, and coping strategies.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

All participants took part in the study voluntarily and provided informed consent. Their data has been anonymized and is handled with care and respect, in full compliance with ethical standards and guidelines. No sensitive data regarding the parents' premature infants was collected, as the study focused solely on their experiences with the sound and light environment to address sleep and interaction issues.

4. RESULTS

We present four main sets of results: (1) key findings from participant responses gathered during the discovery research, (2) relevant observations from participant responses during the participatory ideation process, as well as design considerations, (3) the concept proposal, and (4) implications of using ASP during kangaroo care. The ASP engagement and concept proposal is described in greater detail in a forthcoming thesis publication by the first author² as well as in the video prototype.³

4.1 Discovery Research

Five participants (4F, 1M, aged 24–27) completed semi-structured interviews. They reported normal or corrected vision and engaged with ASPs via smartphones, tablets, laptops, wired earphones, and wireless earphones. ASP providers included YouTube Music, Spotify, Deezer, and Apple Podcasts.

Participants integrated audio content (music, podcasts, or both) into various 'contextual situations', such as cooking, cleaning, laundry, showering, studying/working, exercising, social events, and commuting. Their motivations for audio engagement in such scenarios fell into three categories:

² <https://kth.diva-portal.org/smash/search.jsf?dswid=5048>

³ <https://youtu.be/-IQwnVwr8g8>

Focus and Flow: Audio helped sustain attention during activities like studying by blocking distractions.

Motivation: Tasks requiring energy, such as exercising or cleaning, were made more engaging with audio.

Companionship: Audio served as stimulation during repetitive or mechanical tasks.

Participants' likelihood of addressing unpleasant deviations in audio sessions depended on their activity, the perceived severity of the mismatch, and their willingness to interrupt the task:

High cognitive demand (e.g., navigation): Participants often avoided course corrections due to safety concerns or the inability to allocate visual attention to touch-based interactions.

Motivation-driven tasks: Sensitivity to mismatches was high, with participants more likely to course-correct despite interruptions to the contextual situation.

Focus-driven tasks: While engrossed in their activity, participants detected fewer deviations. However, once noticed, they preferred quick, low-effort adjustments to minimize disruption.

Monotonous tasks: Participants were divided between exploring new content and maintaining precise control over their audio experience.

Device affordances, environmental factors (e.g., public spaces), and contextual constraints (e.g., physical limitations during tasks) also shaped participants' corrective actions and tolerance for mismatches in audio preferences.

4.2 Ideation Workshop Outcome

The workshop involved five participants (3F, 2M, aged 23–30), all of whom relied on a combination of YouTube, Spotify, or TikTok as their primary ASP. Participants were divided into two groups—'Group Gym' and 'Group Cooking'—based on their audio engagement habits.

This section consolidates the key findings emerged from the workshop, and the design considerations for developing ASPs suited for such use cases. The considerations are also contextualized in the ABD framework [5, 6], to enable designers prioritizing accessibility in their design cycles.

Artefact Form: Participants envisioned on-body artefacts that track gestures and provide feedback. Group Gym prioritized artefacts that stayed secure during movement, proposing designs that adhered to the body. Group Cooking suggested artefacts to have flexibility: like a band to tie back hair could also be tied around the arm, emphasizing adaptability to different body parts based on user preferences.

When designing on-body artefacts, designers can consider forms that can stay securely on the user's body during movement, offer versatility in how they're worn, and serve functional purposes. This empowers users, while aligning with the ABD principles 'Accountability', 'Adaptation', and 'Transparency' [5, 6].

Body Part Selection: Group Gym excluded arms and legs, opting for head and neck gestures to avoid interference with exercise. Group Cooking preferred head, feet, and mouth gestures due to their unobstructed availability during cooking. These preferences aligned with commonly used

body parts in gesture-interaction protocols noted in prior studies [28].

For gesture design, prioritizing body parts minimally engaged in the main activity avoids interruptions and improves accessibility. This supports the 'Ability' principle of the ABD framework [5, 6] by leveraging available user capabilities.

Gesture Complexity: For commands involving variables like intensity or time, participants preferred parameterized gestures that conveyed more than binary inputs. These often relied on relative positioning of body parts to communicate dynamic information [24].

For gesture design in these cases, complex, parameterized gestures can be used to convey rich information efficiently, reducing reliance on fallback interfaces. This aligns with the ABD principles 'Ability' and 'Performance' [5, 6].

Intuitive Gestures: Participants favored gestures with natural, intuitive mappings to commands. Metaphorical gestures, based on prior interactions with digital systems, were the most popular.

Incorporating gestures based on familiar metaphors or cultural norms eases learning and recall—critical for SII-friendly interaction. The ASP interaction should tailor mappings to users' cultural contexts or provide customization options. This reflects 'Accountability', 'Adaptation', 'Transparency', and 'Performance' [5, 6].

Accidental Activations: Distinct, deliberate gestures were preferred to avoid false positives during overlapping movements. For example, Group Cooking designed a drag-action foot gesture for skipping songs that wouldn't interfere with typical kitchen activities. Group Gym proposed abstract gestures, such as finger rotations, to prevent disruptions during workouts.

Designers can also prevent unintended triggers through incorporating delimiter gestures, and improve reliability and user control. This aligns with the ABD principle 'Ability' [5, 6].

Complementary Gestures: Commands with opposite effects (e.g., skip forward/backward) were consistently, for all groups, paired with complementary gestures across groups for intuitive interaction.

Using reversible, complementary gestures (e.g., swipe left/right for "previous/next") to enhance learnability and recall reduces cognitive load. This reflects 'Ability', 'Accountability', and 'Transparency' according to the ABD framework [5, 6].

Audio Feedback: Participants noted that implicit feedback from audio changes (e.g., play/pause) often sufficed. For less obvious commands, explicit audio cues were proposed, such as ascending/descending pitch sequences to indicate session start/end. Subtle, affirming sounds like a soft "pling" were preferred for actions such as liking a song.

This shows that incorporating clear, unobtrusive sound cues can balance clarity and recall. Exploring earcons for accessible, hierarchical feedback aligns with the ABD principles 'Accountability' and 'Transparency' [5, 6].

Speech Feedback: Speech feedback was suggested for commands where auditory changes weren't apparent.

Designers can use speech for high-density, abstract, or

time-sensitive feedback, and offer user customization (e.g., voice tone, speed) to ensure inclusion. This aligns with all ABD principles [5, 6].

Visual Feedback: Group Cooking proposed minimizing visual distractions by relying on other modalities (e.g., audio, tactile). For example, tactile cues like temperature variations in slippers reinforced selections. Group Gym envisioned a compact, gesture-activated visual interface with eye-tracking for hands-free exploration.

This points designers to reflect on the use of visual feedback, choosing it only when needed and integrate multiple modalities for flexibility. This supports ‘Ability’ and ‘Adaptation’ [5, 6].

Haptic Feedback: Pressure or temperature changes, was integrated to supplement other modalities. Groups used tactile signals to convey additional information, such as temporal fluctuations or discrete sensations (e.g., hot/cold). However, haptics were primarily employed as a supporting rather than a standalone modality.

Designers can utilize haptic feedback sparingly for time-sensitive or private notifications, and enable frequency adjustments to balance reinforcement and energy efficiency. This reflects the ‘Adaptation’ principle [5, 6].

4.3 The Concept Proposal

Next, we present the proposed concept, developed by combining the findings and considerations outlined in previous sections with insights from prior research. Through the design choices made during the conceptualization and prototyping stages, we hypothesize that this concept represents one possible approach to improving the usability and accessibility of ASPs for users experiencing SIIs.

The proposal includes a multimodal watch interface with visual, audio, speech, and haptic feedback to support engagement under SIIs. The system offers two interaction modes: *Same-Side Interaction* and *Opposite-Side Interaction*. Same-side, ideal for one-handed use, combines a watch and an optional sensor-embedded ring for precise input (see Fig. 1, upper left, [II] and [III]), with both devices using embedded IMUs for gesture and tilt detection. Opposite-side interaction involves the free hand alongside the watch and relies solely on the watch for input (see Fig. 1, upper left, [I]), catering to users who prefer or need both hands. Users can interact with the devices standalone or as a pseudo-remote for a streaming device. The descriptions and images here assume the watch is worn on the left hand.

This multimodal watch interface hosts two interactive tiles: the ‘Wall Tile’ (see Fig. 1, up and center) for browsing curated content collections, and the ‘Play Tile’ (see Fig. 1, upper right) for managing the current listening session. These tiles are visualised to act as ‘two sides of a coin’, allowing quick switching between them.

The ‘Wall Tile’ organizes collections (songs, playlists, albums curated by the user) in two circular rings (inner: up to five, outer: up to seven), with a non-interactive anchor at 9 o’clock showing playback status. The gestures and the gesture-interaction mappings designed around this tile concern broader navigation and selection. Each gesture initiates a distinct response from the interface, such as a visual

cue for a new recommendation queue, audible feedback confirming the success of an action, or haptic vibrations indicating transitions between sections.

The ‘Play Tile’ displays track metadata, cover art (doubling as a dynamic timeline), and a volume control arc. Users can perform auditory controls such as play/pause, skipping tracks, or altering volume here. The Play/Pause icon shifts to functions like Skip, Fast-Forward, or Reverse via gestures and also serves as a cursor for volume adjustments. For this tile, gestures designed involve hand movements such as single squeezes, rotating the wrist, and other fine motor actions like tapping and flicking. Each action is accompanied by specific user feedback, including visual changes in the cursor icon, auditory confirmations, or tactile responses (e.g., haptic feedback). For instance, rotating the wrist adjusts the volume along a tilt-based axis, rotating the forearm refreshes the content queue, while a single squeeze can activate or deactivate cursor mobility. These feedback mechanisms ensure users receive clear confirmation of their interactions and enhance the overall usability of the system.

A centrally located cursor, based on the ObjectPoint model [19], supports tilt-based same-side interaction, and we introduce “magnetic” properties for snapping to actionable sectors. We also introduce haptic feedback from embedded actuators, along with audio, speech cues to help users navigate effectively, even with limited visual attention.

The concept designates a triple-pinch gesture by the watch hand as the delimiter gesture. This activates the watch and sensors to interpret subsequent gesture-actions. An example interaction sequence utilizing same-side interaction is demonstrated in Fig. 1.

A companion smartphone interface allows users to personalize the experience to complement their own abilities and needs. Users can curate Wall Tile content, pre-specifying playlists and albums to match their preferences. They can optimize the tile layouts and gesture recognition by selecting the preferred watch-wearing hand and choose between same-side or opposite-side interaction modes, which adjust device pairing and sleep mode settings. Feedback customization options conceptualised include haptic feedback frequency, selecting from three voice accents, and choosing one of five speech feedback speeds, ensuring a flexible and accessible interface.

4.4 Findings and Implications for Kangaroo Care

We recruited participants from a pool of 25 parents (mothers) who had experienced prolonged visits (average ten weeks) at a neonatal care unit; this included both intensive care (average two weeks, typically less than one week) and family-type rooms. We conducted eight interviews, received additional comments, and collected 14 completed questionnaires using the 5-point Likert-scale. All reported having used kangaroo care to a very large degree, and primarily in a reclined sitting position, and all had experienced sleep disorders during this time.

According to the interviews, the two main factors that disrupted sleep or rest were related to stress, and to necessary nursing, such as breastfeeding, nasogastric feeding, breast pumping, and similar recurring activities, confirmed

Figure 1. *Upper Row*—Left: Proposed devices. Opposite-side interaction mode uses only a watch [I], while same-side interaction pairs a ring [II] with a watch [III]. Center: The 'Wall Tile' on the watch displays collections A1–5 (inner circle) and B1–7 (outer circle), with a non-interactive pink sector at 9 o'clock. The cursor navigates between collections. Right: 'Play Tile' shows audio content, with cover art doubling as a timeline and an arc indicating volume. The central cursor-icon cycles through Reverse, Previous, Play/Pause, Next, and Fast-Forward. *Lower Row*: A visual depiction of the concept in practice: via an example interaction flow of a user engaging with our concept and utilizing same-side interaction mode.

in the questionnaire (mean=4.6). Less pronounced but still important factors were light and sound pollution, and un-scheduled visits from nurses. In the questionnaire, the medical equipment was considered to be disturbing for the parent (mean=3.9), but less so for the child (mean=3.0). One coping strategy against noise that several mentioned in the interview was using an ASP, although the questionnaire showed that they only listen slightly above 'neither often nor seldom' (mean=3.1). Most reported that they needed to pause the playback very often, and a majority that it was difficult to control the device. In addition, several mentioned that eyemasks were used to reduce visual impressions.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Device Choices and Interaction Styles

The decision to not develop custom hardware for the on-body artefact aligns with the ABD principle 'Commodity' [5, 6]. Leveraging the watch, a widely available technology, makes the product available for a broader range of users. The inclusion of same-side and opposite-side interaction modes invokes both the proposed design considerations regarding artefact form, and the principle of 'Adaptation' in the ABD framework. This design choice enables users

to choose between parallel interaction styles based on their situational needs and abilities [5, 6].

The Wall Tile interface demonstrates how a thoughtful layout can improve usability by balancing access to information with reduced visual clutter. Building on circular menus and tilt-based selection accuracy [19], its design addresses the wrist's uneven range of motion by making the 9 o'clock sector non-interactive—a key area of high error for left-handed wearers. This adaptation is hypothesised to better support user interactions when constrained by SIIs, and improve interaction accuracy in such contexts.

Unlike ObjectPoint's freeform cursor movement, we hypothesised the "sticky" model will improve precision and stability. By incorporating multimodal feedback, such as tactile and audio cues, this design also builds on recommendation to enable eyes-free, wrist-only interactions [19].

This proposal uses a gyroscope based on a model which represents hand and arm movements as rotational gestures around joints like the wrist, elbow and shoulder [29], also explored in the Wrist-as-a-Joystick concept [20]. Gyroscopes offer high accuracy in detecting multi-axis rotations, making them ideal for tracking short-duration gestures, compared to accelerometers that are prone to noise or magnetometers that are unreliable in dynamic environments.

Additionally, the gyroscope's ability to recognize gesture patterns with low computational cost reduces energy consumption and eliminates the need for sensor fusion [29], contributing to a more sustainable design.

The triple-pinch was selected as the delimiter gesture for its ease of performance, low risk of accidental activation, minimal movement requirements, and discreetness. It reliably meets criteria for same-side interaction-friendly delimiters [30] and is detectable via gyroscopic data. While their top recommendation, the doubleRotate (Flick Wrist), was considered, its inward/outward variations made it more suitable as complementary gestures for additional actions.

5.2 Implications for Kangaroo Care

The experiences and circumstances of the participants are highly individual and distinct compared to those of parents with full-term babies. As anticipated, many participants highlighted how their mobility was significantly limited due to the need to remain stationary, constrained by the medical equipment cables connected to their bodies, infants, and surrounding furniture. A few still considered that interacting with a mobile phone was unproblematic, but this may either correspond to a very limited use, due to the circumstances, or to using the phone without actually interacting much.

It is beyond reasonable doubt that the light and sound environment in neonatal care units are a stressor to the parents. However, participating mothers report that their main concerns relate to nursing routines; in the interview, they commonly mention that nursing routines are very frequent, up to several times per hour, which implies that these are also the main cause of ASP disruptions. From the questionnaire and interview results, we speculate that these factors are interdependent in terms of being disruptive to sleep and rest, and their combined effect is detrimental. A possible, although small, improvement could therefore be to ease navigation, especially in effortlessly pausing and resuming play by gestures.

Compared to the design concepts presented, the case of kangaroo care would entail a suitable subset of involved body parts and gestures. Arm, torso and head movements are typically restricted, while leg and finger movements are more attainable. Similarly, voice input, as well as feedback in the auditory or haptic domain, are impacted by the low sensory stimulation requirement. Simpler visual feedback could however possibly be part of a design solution.

6. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the impact of situationally-induced impairments on a user's capability to navigate and engage with audio streaming platforms, and the subsequent accessibility challenges they face. Findings from interviews and workshops indicate that traditional ASP interfaces, which are visually intensive and screen-based, often fail to accommodate SIIs and their impact on user abilities. This study advocates for the principles of Ability-Based Design, and proposes considerations for designing more accessible gesture-based interactions and multimodal feedback. We

also present a concept incorporating gesture-based, multi-modal interfaces, and hypothesize how it could provide an avenue for supporting more adaptable and accessible audio interactions for users experiencing SIIs.

While promising, further testing is recommended to validate this conceptual approach and its design choices in a broader range of scenarios and practical settings. Based on our findings, we suggest that the design concept, initially conceived for general users, could also benefit parents in kangaroo care situations, where movement restrictions and the need for a low-sensory environment impact interactions with audio-playing devices. This extreme use case further supports the validity and applicability of the solution.

Future work should include physical prototyping, task-based testing, exploring the role of sound feedback strategies that are adaptive to different situations—encountered, for instance, by parents in kangaroo care. Future work should also involve exploring accessibility for users with a variation of situationally-induced impairments to ensure equitable access for all.

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